

PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF TEACHERS IN EDUCATION

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Abstract. *This article discusses the fundamental changes in education and upbringing in higher education institutions, the integration of these changes into international standards, and the ongoing reforms aimed at preparing highly qualified specialists that meet labor market demands. It also highlights the importance of teachers' professional skills and competencies.*

Keywords: *international standards, teachers' professional skills, teachers' professional competencies, qualified specialists, professional qualification requirements, social cooperation.*

The assertion that the power that strengthens a nation and elevates its people is knowledge, science, education, and upbringing is a truth that requires no proof. Today, the reforms being implemented in our country are aimed at expanding the coverage of higher education for young people, training them with knowledge and skills, and preparing specialists aligned with global development. The increasing attention to science in New Uzbekistan is not without reason. In contemporary life, it is impossible to imagine progress without the advancement of knowledge and education. In leading countries around the world, developing education is prioritized as a foremost task. Indeed, the future prosperity of a nation is closely linked to its achievements in this field.

Certainly, the comprehensive transformation of our country's educational system, its integration into international standards, and the training of highly qualified specialists in accordance with the demands of labor market are reforms being implemented. However, despite this, changes in quality are still not evident. Therefore, it is necessary to establish targeted criteria for training higher-educated professionals and to consider the demands and needs of specialties and programs being introduced in various regions and sectors.

The preparation of specialists in the field of pedagogy is carried out systematically at higher education institutions through educational programs and training paths. Improving the educational process based on foreign experiences, ensuring employment, and systematically directing individuals toward their professions will enhance the quality of education. The goal of higher education institutions is well-known: it is to prepare competitive professionals for the job market by ensuring alignment between professional qualification requirements for pedagogical specialists and participants of educational process through a balance between theory and practice.

The integration of higher education institutions with labor market entities and institutions, government bodies at the national, regional, and local levels, and public organizations holds

significant importance. This process involves coordinating the interests of all participants in this interaction.

Thus, social collaboration in the field of vocational pedagogical education is a collection of mutually beneficial interests and strategic plans aimed at uniting the efforts of future employers, representatives of higher education institutions, and other organizations for the sustainable development of education in the region. It is essential to understand the role of higher pedagogical education in developing social cooperation relations at the regional level in continuously enhancing the professional skills of educators across various disciplines.

For this reason, it is necessary to interpret “social collaboration” as a system based on mutual activities that adhere to developed rules and agreements with a legal framework aimed at uniting resources for common interests and needs in the field of higher pedagogical education. This system should be constructed on a worldview that is characterized by beneficial, constructive, and long-term cooperation among potential employers, higher education institutions, government bodies, and other organizations.

Preparing future educators effectively based on social collaboration requires increasing the role of higher education institutions in regional development efforts while ensuring comprehensive interaction with various social entities while considering traditions in the development of higher pedagogical education. The preparation of pedagogical personnel within the framework of social collaboration can be studied from both external and internal relational perspectives. In working with government bodies, universities have chosen a mutually beneficial cooperation strategy [1;49].

Professional training based on social partnership is also being implemented within the internal educational environment of the university. For this purpose, the following forms of collaboration are being utilized: joint design of academic subjects considering qualification requirements that enable rapid reform of vocational training content, regular discussions held in department meetings, joint seminars dedicated to various issues, and scientific-methodical conferences that allow for the introduction of innovative technologies; publication of joint educational and methodological manuals that optimize the assimilation of course content for students from colleges and pedagogical classes; (for students) general educational and production practices, commercial games, problem-based seminars, creative activities aimed at enhancing research skills, consolidation and practice of knowledge acquired in activities closely related to professional work; interim rating assessments conducted by university teachers to increase students' interest in acquiring competitive professional knowledge, skills, and competencies. The objects of internal interactions based on social partnership are the students.

The work in this area is organized to enhance the theoretical knowledge and methodology skills of general education school teachers in the subjects they teach, introduce methods and techniques for teaching students independent thinking, assist in effective use of methodological manuals created for subjects and available resources during the educational process, prepare teachers for certification exams, as well as establish pathways for their continuous independent learning, and organize ongoing training sessions by methodologists aimed at continuously improving subject teachers' professional skills. [2;247].

In the process of organizing educational activities, attention is paid to the following aspects of the continuous enhancement of future teachers' professional competencies:

- The ability to work with state educational standards, curricula, and programs, organizing lessons based on newly created literature;
- Selecting modern methods and techniques for teaching that correspond to lesson topics;
- Effective use of information and communication technologies, utilizing existing multimedia materials and creating new ones;
- Maintaining educational laboratory equipment and replenishing it as needed;
- Improving skills and competencies in conducting laboratory and practical exercises;
- Filling gaps based on results from knowledge competitions, Olympiads, and monitoring outcomes;
- Working on solving problems and assignments from the curriculum using simple and convenient methods. [3];

In summary, it is necessary for professionals in the field of education to continuously develop their skills in order to meet the objective pace of modern society's demands and achieve the required level of professionalism. The continuous professional growth of a modern educator, who embodies concepts such as professional and personal competence, yields positive results.

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